

Figure 26: sirās, vaṃśas, anuvaṃśas, and marmans in a 9x9 vāstu, DM 79.1-14.

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|-------|----------|---|-----------------|
| — | sirā | ✦ | vajra (ṣaṭkoṇa) |
| | anuvaṃśa | △ | triśūla |
| == | vaṃśa | ✦ | catuska |

Here, I have laid the sirās, vaṃśas, anuvaṃśas and marmans over the cell design of the 9x9 vāstu as seen at figure 6d, so that the positions of the deities named at 79.1-6 may be discerned.

The sandhis are unmarked. I am unsure whether they run along the outside of the deity cells, or through the cell centres, as is the case for the anuvaṃśas.